

A REAL-WORLD USE- CASE ANALYSIS TO STUDY PENETRATION OF INDUSTRY 4.0 ACROSS INDUSTRIES AND SUPPLY CHAINS

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Abstract

Customer environment in today's world is rapidly evolving. Consumers are demanding choice, flexibility & transparency in ways as never before. Industry 4.0 is presenting disruptive opportunities to businesses and supply chains, in their pursuits to eliminate waste, innovate & create customer value. Technological advancements like 3D printing, IOT, Artificial intelligence, Machine Learning, Robotics can completely change the ways of working in most supply chains. While potential benefits of industry 4.0 implementation are quite appealing, the real situation on ground can be better assessed by looking into some real-world applications with a problem-solving lens. This paper aims to bring out through real world examples how Industry 4.0 technologies are resulting in emergence of new business models & not just enabling improvement of existing performance measures. The paper also aims to provide a dipstick check of which amongst the nine Industry 4.0 technologies have currently had highest adoption within industry so far & what aspects of supply chain performance is Industry 4.0 making most impact.

Keywords – Industry 4.0, Supply chain functions, Cyber physical systems

1. Introduction

Global industrial landscape currently is disrupted by the new age technologies. German Govt first coined it in 2011 as the fourth industrial revolution or Industry 4.0. Researchers have defined industry 4.0 as the vision of having inter-connected people and things anytime, anyplace with anything and anyone. It involves the transition from physical processes supported by IT to a world of cyber physical systems (CPS), where physical world is fully integrated with cyber world. It has been estimated that Industry 4.0 could reduce production costs by 10-30%, logistics expenses by 10-30% and quality related costs by significant 10-20%.

Digitalization of supply chains is changing how products are designed, fabricated, used, and serviced, just as it's transforming the operations, processes & energy footprint of factories and supply chains. There are nine key technologies which underpin the Industry 4.0. These are – (1) the internet of things, (2) the cloud, (3) big data analytics, (4) cybersecurity, (5) simulation, (6) additive manufacturing or 3d printing, (7) augmented reality, (8) robot, (9) horizontal & vertical system integration

Digitization can allow companies to fully integrate their supply chains, improve operational processes, making them more adaptive & responsive. While potential benefits of industry 4.0 implementation are quite appealing, the real situation on ground needs a better assessment. This can be best done by looking into some real-world application as that would clarify how exactly these technologies are adding value to real businesses by solving problems on hand & generating exciting newer ways to acquire & serve customers.

Authors of this paper developed a systemic literature review & subsequent analysis to answer below research questions -

- To study real world applications of industry 4.0 technologies beyond theory.

- To develop a good appreciation of how companies across world are embracing new age technologies with a problem-solving lens in Supply Chain management.
- To understand with real use cases how Industry 4.0 technologies are resulting in emergence of new business models & not just enabling improvement of existing performance measures.
- Get a dipstick check of which amongst the nine Industry 4.0 technologies have currently had highest adoption within industry so far.
- Get a dipstick check on what aspects of supply chain performance is Industry 4.0 making most impact across all industries / geographies.

This paper is structured in five sections. After providing an introduction, Section two of the paper outlines the methodology used for this study. An extensive literature review will be presented in section three. Basis literature review research questions will be answered in section four. This will be followed by discussion of key points in section five.

2. Approach

This study has been done by reviewing application of the industry 4.0 technologies across the globe with a strong focus on supply chain management & revenue enhancements, enabled by supply chain processes. Sources of information include research papers, white papers by consulting companies / research scholar / supply chain practitioners, company websites & various reports. These sources of information have been scrutinized with an objective to understand some clear questions like (a) what problems have been attempted to be solved, (b) how the problems were solved & then (c) most importantly how and which industry 4.0 technologies were used for same. Implications of the solutions to the specific aspects of value chain improvement have been also mapped. As an outcome, a rich repository of 50 real world use cases of application has been compiled, which is a great source of knowledge now for all researchers & practitioners.

3. Review of Literature

Authors have summarized a compilation of 50 use cases / real work examples as below -

Solution Title	Company Name	Problem	Industry 4.0 Tech	Value Chain area
Rolls-Royce: Total Care Business Model	Rolls Royce	Traditional maintenance model wasn't satisfactory for Rolls-Royce. Aftermarket revenues were unpredictable	Machine Learning, IoT	MAKE, Sales
Digitizing to improve materials and supply chain management - Alfred (AI Solution)	Thyssen Krupp Materials Services (TKMS)	TKMS needed to fully utilize data insights through algorithms. The plan was to build algorithms to improve materials deployment.	AI & Machine Learning	Plan & deliver
Improving training with IoT and VR technology at BAE Systems	BAE Systems	BAE Systems wanted to leverage AR technology to improve the quality of the finished product, increase assembly speed, and achieve industry compliance.	IoT & VR	HR
IIoT-integrated data backbone at Fast Radius	Fast Radius	Quality & rework improvement in Manufacturing, logistics & capacity optimization,	IOT, Digital Twin, Cloud Computing	MAKE

		inventory reduction, reduce speed to market	, Machine learning	
IIoT academy to drive Fourth Industrial Revolution transformation at Petkim	Petkins	Building organizational capabilities for Digital transformation	Multiple	HR
Connecting the customer with a customer-centric product ecosystem at Haier	Haier	Provide Customized products, customer delight by remote trouble shooting, transforming operational efficiencies	IoT, Cloud, Big Data	Sales, MAKE, Plan
Engaging the customer in product configuration at SAIC Maxus	SAIC Maxus	Providing Differentiated Customer Centric solutions with customized products, reducing speed to market, driving quality improvement & operational efficiency improvements	Cloud, Simulation, AI, Horizontal & Vertical integration	Sales, MAKE, Plan, Quality
Data transparency creating greater value at Phoenix Contact	Phoenix Contact	Delivering Mass customization	IOT, RFID	Sales, MAKE, Plan
Stitch Fix: The Amazing Use Case of Using Artificial Intelligence In Fashion Retail	Stitch Fix	Creating a new business model for superior customer experience & delighting them with designs they really need	AI & Machine Learning	Sales, Plan
How Sephora is leveraging AR and AI to transform retail and help customers buy cosmetics	Sephora	Creating a seamless experience for the customer across both digital and retail outlets.	AR & AI	Sales, Plan
Invisalign – 9/10 dentists recommend additive manufacturing	Align Technology	Providing Innovative & Superior solution to customers	3D Printing	MAKE, Sales
Adding Value across the Value Chain — Additive Manufacturing at Siemens	Siemens	Reduce product development time, reduce spare part costs, reduce material waste	3D Printing	MAKE
XPO Logistics: Attempting to Bring the Truckload and Less-than-Truckload (LTL) Industries into the Twenty-First Century	XPO Logistics	Improve its pricing and capacity utilization for trucking companies	AI & Machine Learning	Deliver

Can machine learning solve the cyber security threat?	Darktrace	With cyber security attacks growing in frequency how will we be able to secure our digital assets when there is also a growing shortage of skilled cyber security professionals?	Cyber security	All
Turning Big Data into Clean Electrons at NextEra	NextEra	As prices drop and competition intensifies in the world of solar and wind, can generators use machine learning to maintain healthy margins?	Big Data, Cloud Computing	Sustainability
RIDGES Run Deep: How PepsiCo Delivered on Crunch through 3D Printing	PepsiCo	Product innovation with rapid prototyping	3D Printing	NPD
Beauty Brand with Drones of Data: How Glossier Employs Machine Learning	Glossier	Revenue enhancement by getting consumer preferences right	Big Data	NPD, Sales
BJC HealthCare adopts IoT for inventory and supply chain management	BJC Healthcare	Optimize inventory to achieve cost-savings in its supply chain.	IOT, RFID	Plan
Big Data decision-making at Bosch Automotive factory in China	Bosch Automotive	Improving manufacturing reliability & overall maintenance costs	Big Data, IoT	MAKE
Volkswagen creates Automotive Cloud	Volkswagen	Product innovation & customer experience improvement	Cloud Computing, IoT, Big Data	MAKE
Fetch Robotics helps DHL improve warehouse operations.	Fetch Robotics	Improving labor productivity in warehouses	Robotics	Deliver
Racing to win with digital twins - Team Penske	Team Penske	Developing cheaper, more resource-efficient product testing process and, a way towards developing faster vehicles.	Simulation	MAKE
AR increases productivity at GE	General Electric (GE)	Productivity improvement, quality improvement in Manufacturing	Augmented Reality (AR)	MAKE
Brick Laying Robots	Construction Robotics	Improve labor costs in construction industry	Robotics	MAKE
Emotionally Aware Vehicles: The Future of Road Safety?	Affectiva	How Emotion Artificial Intelligence can be used to monitor drivers and increase road safety?	AI & Machine Learning	Safety

Coty Cosmetics Saves over \$500K with Mobile Cobot System	Coty	Labor Productivity improvement	Robotics	MAKE
How Augmented Reality Became a Serious Tool for Manufacturing at Siemens	Siemens	Remote trouble shooting of machines	AR	MAKE
Four industrial uses of AR	Emerson Automation	Training workers, assisting workers locating assets, remote trouble shooting , simulation of layouts	AR	MAKE
Wi-Fi-equipped robots triple work efficiency / Autonomous Robots at Alibaba	Alibaba	Enhance efficiency & productivity in an e-commerce warehouse.	Smart Sensors, IoT Robotics	Deliver

4. Analysis & High-Level Insights from the use cases

The 50 real world use cases of industry 4.0 technologies can give some high-level insights with respect to a couple of aspects mentioned below:

- Concentration of technology adoptions in industry – A dipstick check of the relative penetration of the 9 technologies
- Concentration of technology applications – There are applications like machine learning, artificial intelligence, predictive analytics, digital twins etc., which are off shoots of the 9 core technologies. Some broad inferences on intensity of the adoption of these applications can be derived from a analysis of these 50 use cases.
- Concentration of adoption of industry 4.0 technologies in horizontal value chain - A dipstick check of the areas impacted can be conducted, taking these use cases as a base.
- Concentration of adoption of industry 4.0 technologies in vertical value chain - A dipstick check of the areas impacted can be conducted, taking these use cases as a base.

Below analysis & charts have been prepared by using the 50 use cases above as a reference. While the data collected is not big & also determined through a statistical plan but selection of use cases being based focused in industry 4.0 as a cluster of technologies & being done on a random basis, allows some high-level insights to be still drawn as an outcome of this assignment / study.

Spread of 50 use cases analysed across sectors

Chart 1

Chart 2

Chart 3

Chart 4

Chart 5

Some insights drawn from the above charts are as below:

- Technology, Automotive & FMCG companies seem to have a higher level of adoption compared to other industries at a global landscape
- IoT, Cloud computing & Big data seem to be some of the most penetrated technologies, though all others also have a good adoption
- Artificial Intelligence & Machine Learning do seem to be the leading applications of the different technologies of industry 4.0
- In the horizontal value chain areas, procurement seems to be the least penetrated area for all 9 technologies & industry 4.0 in general
- In the vertical value chain, sales do seem to be the leading area where industry 4.0 is making a positive impact on. This is probably because of the newer business opportunities which industry 4.0 opens for all businesses.

5. Conclusion & Discussions

This study provides significant insights to various stakeholders. *For research scholars, this study provides* Awareness of real-world examples will enable them to ask more relevant questions to the experts during research phase of a paper or thesis. Industry agnostic approach of this study helps view the technologies & the applications on a wide canvas, not limited to any one industry type or a sector. Same for geographical spread of the study. *For academia, this study will* with a ready repository of use cases & reduce their time taken to compile good examples for the purpose of student interactions. *For Supply chain Practitioner in Industries, this study will* help them see the emerging trends & potential applications of new age technologies. This would motivate practitioners in restructuring their supply chains with clear roadmaps.

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